

CREATING PRE-, WHILE-, AND POST-READING ACTIVITIES: A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: This article explores the creation of pre-, while-, and post-reading activities in the context of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) and foreign language learning. Drawing on insights from experts in reading comprehension and language pedagogy, this paper examines how these activities can enhance learners' comprehension, engagement, and retention. Additionally, human insights are integrated to provide practical recommendations for implementing these strategies effectively in classrooms.

Keywords: Reading activities, pre-reading, while-reading, post-reading, ESP, language comprehension.

Introduction

Reading is a critical skill in language acquisition, particularly in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) contexts, where learners often require tailored strategies to meet their academic or professional needs. Researchers such as Alderson (1984) and Anderson (1999) emphasize the importance of understanding both the linguistic and cognitive processes involved in reading. However, designing effective reading activities requires not only theoretical knowledge but also practical, human-centered approaches to address diverse learner needs.

Methodology

The study draws on theoretical frameworks from Alderson & Urquhart (1984), Anderson (1999), and Barnett (1989), alongside our practical experiences as educators. Key sources on cognitive approaches to reading, such as Beech & Colley (1987), informed the design of activities tailored to varying proficiency levels. Materials were designed to engage learners cognitively, emotionally, and socially, ensuring their relevance to real-world contexts. To ensure a holistic approach, the study utilized feedback from learners and educators to refine and adapt the activities.

Results and Discussion

Pre-Reading Activities

Pre-reading activities aim to activate background knowledge, set expectations, and generate interest. Alderson (1983) highlights the role of prior knowledge in comprehension, suggesting that learners' familiarity with a topic significantly affects their ability to understand a text. Practical applications include brainstorming, KWL charts (Know, Want to know, Learned), and visual aids like pictures or videos.¹

While theory underscores the importance of activating schema, in practice, activities must also be emotionally engaging. For example, using real-life scenarios or culturally relevant

¹ Alderson, J. C., & Urquhart, A. H. (1983). The effect of background discipline on comprehension: A pilot study. In A. Hughes & D. Porter (Eds.), *Using Reader's Background Knowledge in Language Teaching* (pp. 125-124). London: Macmillan.

examples can make texts more relatable. This approach not only prepares learners linguistically but also builds their confidence.

While-Reading Activities

While-reading activities focus on fostering engagement and supporting comprehension in real-time. Techniques such as skimming for main ideas, scanning for details, and annotating texts are effective strategies. Anderson (1999) notes that interactive techniques, such as question prompts embedded in the text, keep learners focused and encourage critical thinking.²

Educators should recognize the diversity in reading styles and preferences. Some learners may benefit from silent reading, while others thrive in group discussions. Flexibility and responsiveness to individual needs enhance the effectiveness of these activities.

Post-Reading Activities

Post-reading activities aim to consolidate understanding, encourage reflection, and promote application of knowledge. Tasks like summarizing, discussing open-ended questions, or creating visual representations of the text (e.g., mind maps) are particularly useful. Barnett (1989) argues that such activities help learners internalize and retain information.

Post-reading activities should also foster creativity and personal expression. For instance, learners can write their reflections, relate the text to their own experiences, or even critique the author's arguments. This not only deepens comprehension but also develops critical thinking and communication skills.

Conclusion

Designing pre-, while-, and post-reading activities requires a balance between theoretical principles and practical, learner-centered approaches. By integrating insights from researchers like Alderson, Anderson, and Barnett with our human understanding of learners' needs and preferences, we can create activities that are both effective and engaging.

Future research should explore the integration of technology and multimodal resources in reading activities to cater to the evolving needs of digital-age learners.

References:

1. Abdul Ghani, Salwa. (1993). ESP Reading: Some implications for design of materials. *English Teaching Forum*, 7, 42-45.
2. Adams, J. A., & Dwyer, M. A. (1982). *English for Academic Uses*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
3. Alderson, C. (1984). Reading in a foreign language: A reading problem or a language problem. In Alderson, C., & Urquhart, A. H. (Eds.), *Reading in Foreign Language* (pp. 114-141). London: Longman.
4. Alderson, J. C., & Urquhart, A. H. (1983). The effect of background discipline on comprehension: A pilot study. In A. Hughes & D. Porter (Eds.), *Using Reader's Background Knowledge in Language Teaching* (pp. 125-124). London: Macmillan.
5. Allen, F. V. (1983). *Techniques in Teaching Vocabulary*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. Anderson, N. (1999). *Exploring Second Language Reading*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
7. Barnett, M. A. (1989). *More Than Meets the Eye: Foreign Language Reading*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Center for Applied Linguistics.

² Anderson, N. (1999). *Exploring Second Language Reading*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.

8. Barr, P., Clegg, C., & Wallace, C. (1981). Advanced Reading Skills. London: Longman.
9. Bartlett, F. C. (1932). Remembering. London: Cambridge University Press.
10. Beech, J., & Colley, A. (1987). Cognitive Approaches to Reading. Chichester: John Wiley and Sons.

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